

A Kinetic Study for the Fenton and photo-Fenton Paracetamol Degradation in an Annular Photoreactor Involving LVRPA

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A kinetic model for Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of paracetamol (PCT) in an annular photoreactor was proposed. The radiation field inside the reactor was taken into account through the Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption, evaluated by assuming a line source model with spherical and isotropic emission. The proposed kinetic model allowed deriving reaction rates for PCT and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). Different initial concentrations of H_2O_2 and ferrous ion (Fe^{2+}) were tested for a same value of initial concentration of PCT. Experimental data were used to implement a nonlinear regression procedure aiming at finding the correlation between experimental and predicted data. Relative root mean square errors resulted in 9.7% and 6.8% for H_2O_2 and PCT, respectively. Complete PCT removal was achieved under all investigated conditions. Moreover, the use of radiation allowed increasing PCT removal of about 75% and total organic carbon conversion of about 60%.

Introduction

In the last decade, a remarkable experimental effort has been made to better understand the photo-Fenton process as a whole, as pointed out in the review by [1]. Concerning photo-Fenton kinetic modelling, mainly three different model based approaches have been proposed to describe the photo-Fenton process, such as First Principles Models (FPMs) [2], Empirical Models (EMs) [3], and Data Based Models (DBMs) [4]. While currently, EMs and DBMs are unable to fully capture the complexity and nonlinear nature of such processes, the accuracy and understanding that might provide FPMs is unaffordable. Hence, the present study aims at proposing a compromise solution by developing a kinetic model that can describe the Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of Paracetamol (PCT) in an annular photo-reactor and can take into account the Local Volumetric Rate of Photon Absorption (LVRPA) inside the photoreactor. PCT was selected as model contaminant being a widely used antipyretic and analgesic that can be detected in wastewaters and groundwater between 0.05 and 1.9 mg L⁻¹ [5]. Reaction rates for PCT and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) were obtained and ordinary differential equations were derived for describing component mass balances in the reactor. An experimental data set testing the effects of ferrous ion initial concentrations ($C_{Fe^{2+}}^0$), H_2O_2 to PCT initial concentration ratios ($C_{H_2O_2}^0 : C_{PCT}^0$), and radiation levels, was used to fit the model. Hence, experimental and predicted concentrations of PCT and H_2O_2 were compared and relative root mean square errors (%RMSE) were calculated to test model reliability.

Material and Methods

The general methodology consists of an experimental part and a modelling section including model fitting (parameter estimation).

Experimental

The experimental step provides the data that will be used in the final optimisation step to estimate the kinetic parameters of the proposed model. Fenton and photo-Fenton assays were performed in batch mode with recirculation, in a pilot plant consisting in a 15-L system composed by a glass reservoir and an annular photo-reactor equipped with an Actinic BL TL-DK 36 W/10 1SL lamp and an irradiated volume of 1.5L. Initial concentrations of H_2O_2 and Fe^{2+} were varied between 94.5, 189, and 378 mg L⁻¹ and between 5, 7.5, and 10 mg L⁻¹, respectively, for the same value of the initial concentration of PCT (40 mg L⁻¹). The total reaction time was set to 120 min.

Modelling

The modelling section starts by proposing a kinetic model shown in **Table 1** (based on the assumptions by [6]), followed by the reactor model that allows describing, by the means of a set of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs), the mass balances into the photoreactor.

Table 1 Simplified reaction mechanism of Fenton and photo-Fenton PCT degradation.

ID	Reaction steps	Kinetic constants
1	$Fe^{2+} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{3+} + \cdot OH + \cdot OH$	k_1
2	$Fe^{3+} + H_2O \rightarrow Fe^{2+} + \cdot OH + H^+$	ϕ
3	$Fe^{3+} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{2+} + HO_2^{\cdot} + H^+$	k_3
4	$H_2O_2 + \cdot OH \rightarrow HO_2^{\cdot} + H_2O$	k_4
5	$PCT + \cdot OH \rightarrow P_i$	k_5

P_i in the ID 5 of the kinetic model presented in **Table 1**., represents the generic intermediate compound generated by the hydroxyl radical ($\cdot OH$) attack to PCT, ϕ refers to the wavelength-averaged primary

quantum yield that was proposed by [7] and k_1 , k_3 , k_4 , k_5 are the four kinetic parameters accounting for Fenton and Fenton like reactions and $\bullet\text{OH}$ attack to H_2O_2 and PCT, respectively.

The proposed kinetic model was used to obtain the reaction rates for PCT and H_2O_2 . The general reaction rate expression can be written as follows:

$$[R_i(\underline{x}, t)] = [R_i^T(\underline{x}, t)] + \Phi \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$(i = \text{PCT}, \text{H}_2\text{O}_2, \text{Fe}^{2+}, \text{Fe}^{3+})$$

The first term on the right-hand side of **Eq. 1** corresponds to the thermal reaction rate that gives the i -component degradation by the Fenton reaction taking place in the non-irradiated liquid volume (given by the total volume, V_T , minus the irradiated volume, V_{IRR}). Conversely, the second term on the right-hand side corresponds to the i -component degradation by both the radiation activated and thermal reactions (Fenton and photo-Fenton reactions) occurring inside the irradiated liquid volume. Finally, $\sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t)$ (where \underline{x} is a position vector accounting for the radius and the axial coordinates of the reactor) is the LVRPA extended to polychromatic radiations by performing the integration over all useful wavelengths λ (300-420 nm).

The following ODEs system gives the balance equations of the reactor model (**Eqs. 2-7**):

$$\frac{dC_{PCT}}{dt} = \left[\frac{V_{IRR}}{V_T} \left(k_1 C_{Fe^{2+}} C_{H_2O_2} \left(-\frac{1}{\delta} \right) \right) \right] + \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ \left[\left(\frac{V_T - V_{IRR}}{V_T} \right) \left(k_1 C_{Fe^{2+}} C_{H_2O_2} \left(-\frac{1}{\delta} \right) \right) \right] \\ &\frac{dC_{H_2O_2}}{dt} = \left[\frac{V_{IRR}}{V_T} \left(k_1 C_{Fe^{2+}} C_{H_2O_2} \left(-\left(1 + \frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right) \right) \right] + \\ &+ \left[\frac{V_{IRR}}{V_T} \left(-\gamma - \Phi \left\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \right\rangle_{V_{IRR}} \right) \right] + \quad \text{Eq. 3} \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{V_T - V_{IRR}}{V_T} \right) \left(k_1 C_{Fe^{2+}} C_{H_2O_2} \left(-\left(1 + \frac{1}{\rho}\right) \right) - \gamma \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

With the initial conditions

$$C_i = C_i^{t_0} \quad t_0 = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where:

$$\delta = \frac{k_4}{k_5} \frac{C_{H_2O_2}}{C_{PCT}} + 1 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$\rho = \frac{k_5}{k_4} \frac{C_{PCT}}{C_{H_2O_2}} + 1 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\gamma = k_2 C_{Fe^{3+}} C_{H_2O_2} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

It must be noticed that C_i ($i = \text{PCT}, \text{H}_2\text{O}_2, \text{Fe}^{2+}, \text{Fe}^{3+}$) represents the i -component concentration, hence two more differential equations accounting for Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} concentrations were introduced (equations not shown). Moreover, $\langle \sum_{\lambda} e_{\lambda}^a(\underline{x}, t) \rangle_{V_{IRR}}$ is the LVRPA

averaged over the reactor volume, and for simplicity, we will refer to it as $\text{LVRPA}_{V_{IRR}}$.

LVRPA depends on the radiation field within the photoreactor and consequently on the physical properties and geometrical characteristics of the lamp-reactor system. Hence, a radiation model has to be previously introduced. Especially, a line source model with spherical and isotropic emission (LSSE model) was adopted, based on the assumptions proposed by [8]. This allowed to calculate $\text{LVRPA}_{V_{IRR}}$ as a function of Fe^{3+} concentration (this last was considered as the only absorbing specie for $\lambda > 300\text{nm}$) and is shown in **Fig. 1**, where it is possible to observe that as Fe^{3+} concentration increases, the fraction of absorbed radiation increases until a threshold value is reached (corresponding to 750 mg L^{-1}).

Figure 1. $\text{LVRPA}_{V_{IRR}}$ calculated as a function of Fe^{3+} concentration by applying the proposed LSSE radiation model.

Then, a nonlinear multiparameter optimization procedure was applied in order to minimize the differences between the experimental and theoretical values of PCT and H_2O_2 concentrations. The estimated values can be obtained by numerically solving the ODEs system given by **Eqs. 2-7**. A fourth-order explicit Runge-Kutta method was implemented in MATLAB in order to obtain the desired solution. Then, a Newton Gauss-Marquardt algorithm was used to estimate the kinetic constants (k_1 , k_3 , k_4 , k_5) and the relative root mean square errors (**%RMSE**) were calculated to test model reliability.

Results and Discussion

Experimental results have shown that all investigated conditions allowed to achieve the complete removal of PCT within a maximum time of 10 min (Fenton process for the lowest values of $C_{Fe^{2+}}^0$ and $C_{H_2O_2}^0$) and a minimum time of 2.5 min (photo-Fenton process for the highest values of $C_{Fe^{2+}}^0$ and $C_{H_2O_2}^0$).

In **Fig. 2**, the comparison between experimental and predicted concentrations of H_2O_2 and PCT, is shown. The irradiated condition (**A**) led to the complete PCT removal in about 2.5 min while under non irradiated

conditions (B) the total removal of PCT was obtained only in about 10 min (between 7.5 and 10 min). Hence, the photo-Fenton process allowed to increase the PCT removal efficiency of about 75%.

Fig. 2. Experimental concentrations of paracetamol (\circ ●) and hydrogen peroxide (Δ ▲) and predicted concentrations of paracetamol (—) and hydrogen peroxide (---). Fenton (\circ Δ) and photo-Fenton (\bullet ▲) process. **A)** $C_{Fe^{2+}}^0 = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $C_{H_2O_2}^0 = 378 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ **B)** $C_{Fe^{2+}}^0 = 5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and $C_{H_2O_2}^0 = 189 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$.

The comparison between experimental and predicted values of C_i ($i = \text{PCT}, \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$) allowed the estimation of

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k_1, k_3, k_4 and k_5 resulting in 147.3, 3.2, $7.0E+07$, and $3.6E+09 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, in agreement with the range of values found in the literature [9].

As can be noticed, the proposed model shows a relative good agreement with the experimental results, which was also confirmed by the %RMSE values that, taking into account all the experimental runs (Fenton and photo-Fenton), resulted in 9.7% and 6.8% for H_2O_2 and PCT, respectively. Regarding the total organic carbon (TOC) conversion (X_{TOC}), a value of 43%, 51% and 57%, was achieved after 45 min of reaction (time at which the complete consumption of the oxidant occurred) by performing photo-Fenton treatment with the highest value of $C_{H_2O_2}^0$ (378 mg L^{-1}) and increasing the value of $C_{Fe^{2+}}^0$ from 5 to 7.5 and 10 mg L^{-1} , respectively. This means that an increase of TOC conversion of about 30% was obtained by increasing $C_{Fe^{2+}}^0$. However, by applying the Fenton process, a minimum value of X_{TOC} (about 20%) was achieved. Hence, in terms of X_{TOC} , the use of radiation allowed increasing the removal performance of about 60%.

Conclusions

Results have shown that the proposed kinetic model for predicting Fenton and photo-Fenton PCT degradation in an annular photoreactor, is able to capture the complex and nonlinear nature of such processes jointly with the effect of LVRPA.

Kinetic parameters, accounting for the Fenton and Fenton-like reaction and the $\cdot\text{OH}$ attack to PCT and H_2O_2 , were estimated.

Values of %RMSE resulted in 9.7% and 6.8% for H_2O_2 and PCT, respectively.

Complete PCT removal was achieved under all investigated conditions within a maximum time of 10 min (Fenton process) and a minimum time of 2.5 min (photo-Fenton process).

Photo-Fenton process allowed increasing PCT removal efficiency of about 75% and TOC conversion of about 60%.

This model will be the starting point for the development of a more complex model accounting also for the reaction rates of intermediate compounds and TOC.

Photo-Fenton degradation of the herbicide 2,4-D for conditions of natural pH and presence of inorganic anions

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The photo-Fenton degradation of the herbicide 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) for naturally groundwater conditions is presented. A kinetic model derived from a reaction sequence is proposed to study the influence of the commonly anions (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- and NO_3^-) present in this type of waters using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source and conditions of pH close to neutrality. Applying a nonlinear regression procedure, a good correlation was obtained between the experimental data and the results obtained with the model. The errors (RMSE) obtained were 4.48×10^{-3} mM, 3.29×10^{-3} mM, 2.54×10^{-3} mM and 4.72×10^{-3} mM for 2,4-D, Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- and NO_3^- , respectively. It was found that the photo-Fenton process is effective in the degradation of the herbicide employing a groundwater matrix when ferrioxalate is used as the catalyst source. A reduction of only 14.3 % in the conversion of 2,4-D after 180 min of reaction was observed when evaluating the system with the mixture of all the anions.

Introduction

The photo-Fenton process is widely used for the treatment of contaminants present in water. An interesting and potentially useful modification is the use of iron complexes as catalyst source. Previous studies of the group demonstrated the advantages of applying the oxalate ion as an organic ligand for the degradation of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) in aqueous medium at pH = 5 [1].

The presence of inorganic anions in natural waters can affect reaction rates in the photo-Fenton process by: (i) formation of photochemical non-active Fe complexes, (ii) scavenger of OH^\bullet radicals and formation of less reactive radicals, and (iii) Fe precipitation reactions, among others [2].

In this work, 2,4-D photo-Fenton degradation at pH = 5 was studied using a laboratory-scale reactor and a solar simulator, evaluating the effect of different anions (Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- and NO_3^-) in concentrations normally present in groundwater [3].

Material and Methods

Kinetic studies were performed in a lab-scale flat plate reactor of borosilicate glass with external recycle. The storage tank includes a pH-meter, a thermometer and a liquid sample valve. A thermostatic bath was used to ensure constant temperature during the reaction and a centrifugal pump to achieve a high recirculation flow rate and good mixing conditions. The total volume of the treated solution was 3.0 L, while the irradiated reactor volume was 0.07 L [1]. See Figure 1.

A solar simulator (Oriel, model 9600) was used as the irradiation source. The attenuation filter combination: water filter, air mass filter AM0 and air mass filter AM1.5 Direct, (F1.5D) was studied. With the selection of this filter combination, it is intended to simulate solar radiation levels often found in Santa Fe city, Argentina ($31^\circ 39' \text{ S}$, $60^\circ 43' \text{ W}$, 25 m above sea level) in winter conditions.

Figure 1. Scheme of the experimental device. (1) flat plate photoreactor, (2) lamp housing, (3) collimator, (4) water filter, (5) filter holder, (6) heat exchanger, (7) thermostatic bath, (8) recirculation pump, (9) storage tank, (10) thermometer, (11) pH-meter, and (12) sample collection.

With the aid of a modular USB spectrometer (Ocean Optics, USB2000), the local radiation flux averaged over the reactor window (q_w) was measured between 300 and 500 nm, obtaining a value of $3.64 \times 10^{-8} \text{ E cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (31.6 W m^{-2}).

For all tests, the conditions of operation were: $T = 35^\circ \text{ C}$, $[\text{2,4-D}] = 30 \text{ ppm}$, molar ratio of initial concentrations $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{2,4-D} = 28.5$, $[\text{Fe (III)}] = 3 \text{ ppm}$ and $\text{pH} = 5$. Six experiments were carried out, analyzing the presence of each anion individually or all of them together, and compared with the reaction in the absence of them. The anion concentrations in the prepared synthetic groundwater were 88, 55, 100 and 25 ppm for Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , HCO_3^- and NO_3^- , respectively.

Also, to ensure the stabilization of iron in solution throughout the reaction, it was necessary to use a molar ratio $\text{Ox}/\text{Fe} = 10$ (exceeding the stoichiometric value).

Results and Discussion

The main reactions involved in the system are summarized in Table 1. The degradation rate expressions of 2,4-D, 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP), hydrogen peroxide (HP), oxalate (Ox) and anion species (A^{n-}) (NO_3^- ; Cl^- ; HCO_3^- and SO_4^{2-}) can be written by using the matrix representation as indicated in eq. 1 [1]. Here, the inhibitor effects of the anionic species A^{n-} were attributed to: (i) formation of less reactive radicals species ($A^{*(n-1)-}$) and, (ii) hydroxyl radical scavenger [4].

For the kinetic studies performed in the lab-scale flat plate reactor, the mass balances and the initial conditions are given by the set of first order, ordinary differential eqs. 2 and 3 (matrix notation). The kinetic parameters were estimated from experimental and kinetic model results by applying the nonlinear regression procedure of Newton Gauss-Marquardt (Table 2).

$$\mathbf{R}(x,t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \mathbf{R}^{lr}(x,t) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{C}(t) = \mathbf{R}^T(t) + \frac{V_{lr}}{V} \mathbf{R}^{lr}(x,t) \quad (2) \quad \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}^0 \quad t=0 \quad (3)$$

Equation 1 is solved to obtain the mathematical expressions of $R_i(x,t)$. To do this, the steady state approximation (SSA) may be applied for highly reactive radicals and anions species; it was experimentally corroborated that the concentration of the anions remains constant throughout the reaction (see eq. 4). In addition, only the reaction constants of each anion (separately) with the OH^\bullet radicals were estimated. The others values have been taken from previous work [1].

The first term on the right-hand side of eq. 1 or 2, corresponds to the thermal reaction rate. For example, for HP it may be represented by eq. 5. The expression for de OH^\bullet radicals is given by eq. 6. In these equations it is important to clarify that the sum indicates the influence of all anions together.

Table 1. Reaction scheme of 2,4-D degradation

Nº	Reaction step	Estimated kinetic parameter ^a
0	$Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} \xrightarrow{h\nu} Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + CO_2 + 1.5C_2O_4^{2-}$	$\bar{\Phi}_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)} = 1.21 molE^{-1}$ $\bar{\Phi}_{C_2O_4^{2-}} = 1.05 molE^{-1}$
1	$Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4) + 2C_2O_4^{2-} + OH^\bullet + OH^-$	$k_1 = 7.00 \times 10^{-2} M^{-1} s^{-1}$
2	$Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4) + H_2O_2 + 2C_2O_4^{2-} \rightarrow Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-} + OH^\bullet + OH^-$	$k_2 = 3.10 \times 10^4 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
3	$H_2O_2 + OH^\bullet \rightarrow O_2^\bullet + H^+$	$k_3 = 3.76 \times 10^7 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
4	$2,4-D + OH^\bullet \rightarrow 2,4-DCP$	$k_4 = 3.00 \times 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
5	$2,4-DCP + OH^\bullet \rightarrow products$	$k_5 = 2.38 \times 10^{10} M^{-1} s^{-1}$
6	$C_2O_4^{2-} + OH^\bullet \rightarrow 2CO_2 + OH^-$	$k_6 = 7.70 \times 10^6 M^{-1} s^{-1}$
7	$A^{n-} + OH^\bullet \rightarrow A^{*(n-1)-} + OH^-$	$k_{7,A^{n-}}$ (to be estimated for each anion)
8	$A^{*(n-1)-} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow A^n + HO_2^\bullet + H^+$	$k_{8,A^{*(n-1)-}}$

^a Values taken from Conte et al., 2016

Figure 2 shows experimental data and kinetic model predictions of 2,4-D, 2,4-DCP, HP and Ox concentrations for R=28.5, pH=5 and T=35 °C. Keys: (—) Model results, (●) 2,4-D, (♦) 2,4-DCP, (▲) HP, (■) Ox.

Figure 2. Model and experimental results for 2,4-D, 2,4-DCP, HP and Ox concentrations for R=28.5, pH=5 and T=35 °C. Keys: (—) Model results, (●) 2,4-D, (♦) 2,4-DCP, (▲) HP, (■) Ox.

From Figure 2, a 2,4-D conversion after 180 min of reaction ($X_{2,4-D}^{180 min}$) of 63.6 % was observed when

the influence of all anions is evaluated. This represents a reduction of only 14.3 % in the herbicide conversion with respect to the blank test without anions ($X_{2,4-D}^{180 min} = 74.2\%$).

Also, a good agreement between kinetic model predictions and experimental data, considering the influence of all the anions on the system, is observed (RMSE_{2,4-D} = 3.98×10^{-3} mM, RMSE_{HP} = 1.83×10^{-1} mM, RMSE_{Ox} = 1.39×10^{-2} mM, and RMSE_{2,4-DCP} = 5.59×10^{-3} mM).

Furthermore, the $X_{2,4-D}^{180 min}$ obtained individually for each anion was 71.6, 71.0, 68.0 and 66.7 % for HCO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- and Cl^- , respectively.

$$C_{A^{n-}} = \frac{k_{7,A^{n-}} C_{A^{n-}} C_{OH^{\bullet}}}{k_{8,A^{n-}} C_{HP}} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{HP}^T(t) = -C_{HP} \left(k_3 C_{OH^{\bullet}} + k_1 C_{Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}} + k_2 C_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)} \right) - \sum_{i=1}^4 k_{7,A^{n-}} C_{OH^{\bullet}} C_{A^{n-}} \quad (5)$$

$$C_{OH^{\bullet}} = \left[\frac{k_1 C_{Fe^{(III)}(C_2O_4)_3^{3-}} C_{HP} + k_2 C_{Fe^{(II)}(C_2O_4)} C_{HP}}{k_3 C_{HP} + k_4 C_{2,4-D} + k_5 C_{2,4-DCP} + k_6 C_{C_2O_4^{2-}} + \sum_{i=1}^4 k_{7,A^{n-}} C_{A^{n-}}} \right] \quad (6)$$

Table 2. Estimated kinetic parameters and RMSE obtained for each anion

Anion (A^{n-})	Estimated kinetic parameter ($k_{7,A^{n-}}$) ($M^{-1}s^{-1}$)	RMSE _{2,4-D} (mM)	RMSE _{HP} (mM)	RMSE _{ox} (mM)	RMSE _{2,4-DCP} (mM)
NO ₃ ⁻	$k_{7,NO_3^-} = 1.44 \times 10^7$	4.72×10^{-3}	4.29×10^{-2}	9.08×10^{-3}	6.33×10^{-3}
Cl ⁻	$k_{7,Cl^-} = 2.85 \times 10^7$	4.48×10^{-3}	8.68×10^{-2}	1.75×10^{-2}	4.76×10^{-3}
HCO ₃ ⁻	$k_{7,HCO_3^-} = 1.22 \times 10^7$	2.54×10^{-3}	1.46×10^{-1}	1.08×10^{-2}	5.96×10^{-3}
SO ₄ ⁻²	$k_{7,SO_4^{2-}} = 9.97 \times 10^6$	3.29×10^{-3}	8.33×10^{-2}	4.74×10^{-3}	5.65×10^{-3}

Conclusions

A theoretical and experimental study of the homogeneous photo-Fenton degradation of the herbicide 2,4-D is presented. A reaction sequence was proposed using the ferrioxalate complex as iron source for real groundwater conditions; i.e., natural pH and common inorganic anions. A good agreement between kinetic model results and experimental data was observed. It should be noted that the presence of the oxalate ion in the medium, besides allowing the iron catalyst to remain in solution, avoids the formation of iron species less reactive with the anions present. Taking into account the results obtained in the work, we can affirm the effectiveness of photo-Fenton process in the treatment of contaminated real groundwater.

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Dear
L. Conte

The scientific committee of the **3rd Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies (III Cipoa)** in Guatapé, Colombia, November 14-17, 2017, is pleased to announce that your work titled *Photo-fenton degradation of the herbicide 2,4-D for conditions of natural pH and presence of inorganic anions* has been **accepted** under the category of Oral presentation. Please proceed with the corresponding corrections (if it applies to you) and send the corrected abstract to submcipoa2017@gmail.com until August 31, 2017.

The academic schedule for the event is currently under construction. We will send you the information once the schedule is ready so you may check your presentation's date and time.

We would like to remind the authors to register on our website before September 20, 2017. The work will be included in the congress' program after the author proceeds with the inscription. The work will only be included in the book of abstracts if one of the authors pays for the registration fee.

We look forward to meeting you.

Yours sincerely,

Scientific Committee
3rd Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies
(III Cipoa)

Medellín, Colombia
August 14, 2017

Dear
L. Conte

The scientific committee of the **3rd Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies (III Cipoa)** in Guatapé, Colombia, November 14-17, 2017, is pleased to announce that your work titled *A kinetic study for the Fenton and photo-Fenton paracetamol degradation in an annular photo reactor involving LVRPA* has been **accepted** under the category of Short-oral presentation. Please proceed with the corresponding corrections (if it applies to you) and send the corrected abstract to submcipoa2017@gmail.com until August 31, 2017.

The academic schedule for the event is currently under construction. We will send you the information once the schedule is ready so you may check your presentation's date and time.

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**UNIVERSIDAD
DE ANTIOQUIA**

Facultad de Ciencias Exactas
y Naturales

The Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences of the University of Antioquia

Certifies that

LEANDRO OSCAR CONTE

as

PRESENTER

Participated in the 3rd Iberoamerican Conference on Advanced Oxidation Technologies (III Cipoa) and 2nd Colombian Conference on Advanced Oxidation Processes (II Ccpaox), which took place in Guatapé, Colombia during November 14, 15, 16 and 17 of 2017, corresponding to 33 hours

Nora Restrepo

Dean of the Faculty of Exact and Natural
Sciences of the University of Antioquia

Ricardo Antonio Torres

Congress Coordinator CIPOA 2017